

DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS OF TOURISM IN ASIAN COUNTRIES

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ABSTRACT

This article sheds light on the factors that affect the growth and sustainable development of Asian countries in the field of tourism. It is also explained how Asian countries were able to connect their economy with tourism during this period and how they were able to develop it even in difficult situations.

Asia on Tour demonstrates why a reevaluation of the analysis and understanding of tourism is necessary in light of the fast increase of leisure and recreational travel in Asia, since the majority of academic theory on tourism is based on "Western" travelers. Examining both domestic and intraregional tourism, the book shows how millions of Asians are now able to travel as tourists thanks to advancements in infrastructure, rising disposable incomes, liberalized economies, globalization's interconnectivities, and the lowering of political and physical borders. The twenty-three readable essays in this volume, which draw on multidisciplinary theoretical perspectives and current empirical research, show why a thorough and critical examination of Asian tourism is essential to understanding both this quickly changing region and global tourism in the twenty-first century. As an extensive compilation of writings centered. Both rural and urban regions of Southeast Asia provide a wealth and diversity of natural, tangible, and intangible cultural tourism resources. The area's distinctive legacy is emphasized and reflected in the eleven natural and seventeen cultural heritage sites that have been placed on the UNESCO World Heritage List. Intermingled with its ecological legacy is an abundant and varied native ethnic culture with overlays influenced by European, Asian, Indian, and Arab cultures. The region is enhanced by its exceptional natural heritage, its rural landscapes, its lively metropolitan centers, and its vernacular architecture, music, literature, and indigenous knowledge. Buddhist, Hindu, Muslim, and Christian religious traditions are all present.

-Travel and the Community of ASEAN

One of the areas prioritized for integration by 2015 under the pillar of the ASEAN Economic Community is tourism. All ASEAN members' economies depend heavily on tourism, although it is particularly significant in Thailand, Cambodia, Lao PDR, Malaysia, the Philippines, and the Philippines, where it accounts for more than 10% of GDP¹, and makes a

substantial employment contribution to their economies. The WTTC estimates that in 2013, the ASEAN Member States earned US\$112.6 billion in foreign exchange earnings from tourism exports and \$294.4 billion in value added from travel and tour operations, retail, entertainment, transportation, and other tourism-related service and productive sectors. These figures accounted for 12.30% of the regional GDP.

-Current Growth Patterns and Projections

Figure 1 depicts the development of foreign tourist arrivals over time. As previously mentioned, overall arrivals in 2012 have already surpassed the AATSP 2011-2015 prediction of 86.7 million by 2015. Although the proportion of the top three travel destinations—Malaysia, Singapore, and

Thailand's share of all arrivals fell from 70.71% in 2010 to 64.1% in 2014. Cambodia, Myanmar, and Vietnam benefited most from rising to *Data from 2001 to 2012 reflect arrivals by air only for Brunei Darussalam The ASEAN region has significantly increased its share of global and Asia Pacific regional arrivals and receipts from 2010 to 2014 as shown in Figures 2 and 3. UNWTO data indicate that leisure travel is the main purpose of travel for 56% of arrivals in the Asia Pacific Region, followed by visiting friends and relatives at 26%, and business at 16%.

Source of basic data: UNWTO Highlights 2015 Edition

The major source market is intra-ASEAN with 46% share of total international visitor arrivals to ASEAN in 2014. The markets of Asia (30% excluding ASEAN), Europe (12%), Oceania (4%) and America (4%) account for 50% of total arrivals. It is noted that the fastest growing country markets between 2010 and 2013 were China (+30.92%), Japan (+12.95%), Republic of Korea (+10.49%), Taiwan (+9.14%), and Australia (+8.24%). According to the UNWTO, total international arrivals to ASEAN are expected to increase to 123 million by 2020, 152 million by 2025, and 187 million by 2030. This raises issues concerned with the long term sustainability of this growth, most especially the management of relatively static

heritage tourism resources, increased distribution of direct and indirect income and employment benefits to less advantaged populations in the region.

Table 1 – Forecasts of International Arrivals to Southeast Asia in 2020, 2025 and 2030

Region	Projected Growth in Arrivals		Actual		Projections	
	2010-2020	2020-2030	2013	2020	2025	2030
World	3.8%	2.9%	1,087	1,360	1,569	1,809
Asia and Pacific	5.7%	4.2%	248	355	436	535
Southeast Asia	5.8%	4.3%	102*	123	152	187

Subregional Travel Destinations

1. The GMS was the largest of the three subregional groupings in terms of ASEAN arrivals, accounting for 45.9% of total arrivals, \$39.7 billion in visitor exports, 12.1% of subregional GDP (roughly 35% of total ASEAN tourism GDP), and directly employing 3.31 million people (between 50 and 70% are female). This information is based on comparative data available for 2010.

2. Although the BIMP-EAGA and IMT-GT's shares of ASEAN foreign arrivals are smaller than the GMS's, their GDP shares are greater, and the BIMP-EAGA is growing at a quicker rate. At least half of the workers in the subregion's tourist sector are women, and in Thailand, the Philippines, and Vietnam, women hold 60% or more of the positions in the hospitality sector.

3. Job-specific gender profile.

One of ASEAN's main competitive advantages, according to surveys and reports on global competitiveness, is its rich natural and cultural legacy. The legislative framework, human resources, business environment, and infrastructure are the key areas of vulnerability. For ASEAN, creating high-quality travel experiences and goods continues to be a significant problem. The uneven distribution of tourism flows throughout the area is a reflection of the less developed Member States' poor performance. As a result, the task at hand is to make the tourism industry in the impacted Member States more competitive in order to achieve a more equitable distribution of benefits in relation to variables like population density and resource capacity. Therefore, marketing, product development, investments, quality tourism, human resources, and connectivity are the main areas of concentration to increase competitiveness.

MARKETING

Whilst considerable activity has taken place, and specific projects pursued by the MCWG, it is noted that:

- There is a dearth of market research to guide product development, packaging, pricing, distribution and promotion.
- There is a need to better coordinate the activities of the PDWG and that of the MCWG in terms of the marketing function and to ensure that these are combined in the marketing strategy and plan.
- The Acronym "ASEAN" is in fact not known to most consumers of ASEAN tourism who are more familiar with the regional name Southeast Asia or specific countries therein having learned of these at school or in current affairs. The website www.aseantourism.travel therefore does not show up in travel searches on SEA travel, SEA vacations, visit SEA, SEA trips or SEA tours, and thus is not an effective way to promote ASEAN destinations and

products. It is recommended that the European Union approach be adopted—see <http://www.visiteurope.com/en/>, i.e. visitsoutheastasia.com, etc.

- The current list of regional and subregional destination/circuit/corridors and related product themes needs to be augmented with destinations/corridors and related products that better coincide with the less developed destinations of the region—notably where much of ASEAN's poor live

QUALITY TOURISM

The creation and execution of the certification procedures are the largest obstacle to meeting high levels of quality. The difficulty originates from the fact that ASEAN nations have different certification programs and degrees of importance for delivering efficient certification programs because of problems with resources, such as money and labor.

While certification is required in certain nations, it is optional in others. Similarly, as highlighted in the ATSP 2011-2015, it is imperative to provide quantifiable benchmarks and metrics for every region and ensure their transparency to visitors during their decision-making process. There is room for ASEAN to work together more to support the ASEAN focal points for consumer complaints and take into account setting up a system for agencies to exchange information.

ACCESSIBLE TRAVEL

Encouraging travelers to select ASEAN regional products over alternatives, extend their stay, and spend more money in the region requires smooth cross-border travel and cost-competitive thanks to allowing border control regulations and processes as well as well-connected air, sea, and land destinations. The majority of ASEAN Member States still demand visas for citizens of non-ASEAN nations as well as for certain citizens of ASEAN. This lowers the region's price competitiveness as a destination, increases the cost and inconvenience of visiting numerous countries, especially for long-haul markets, and undermines the objective of inclusive economic development.

Given that the delivery of cross-border immigration, quarantine, and security (CIQS) services is not under the jurisdiction of

In my conclusion, The final section of the collection examines the situation of tourism theory today and how Asian travel defies many of the conventions and presumptions that are associated with it. Winter contends in the Conclusion that Anglo-Western centrism still plagues tourism scholarship. He therefore promotes pluralism as an antidote to these dynamics of core and periphery. He highlights some of the prospects and problems for the long-term development of grounded, critical study and education on Asian tourism, given that the consequences of the industry are still very much in flux. According to Winter, taking these kinds of steps is essential if we are to fully comprehend the significant societal changes that Asian tourism is currently bringing about and simultaneously get over the racial, cultural, and regional biases that underlie the majority of current tourism research.

References:

1. Southeast Asia journal. For General Information on ASEAN, please log in www.asean.org

2. <https://www.adb.org/news/leaders-discuss-role-tourism-asia-and-pacifics-development-future>
3. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/strategic-insights-hoteliere-navigating-asias-tourism-kipping-vsgzf>
4. <https://www.adb.org/news/leaders-discuss-role-tourism-asia-and-pacifics-development-future>
5. Conference: Asia's Tourism Potential - Path to Economic Development At: Bengaluru
6. Center for American Progress. (2015). Understanding China's Belt and Road Initiative: Opportunities and Risks. Retrieved from <https://cdn.americanprogress.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/09/22064156/SilkRoad-brief.pdf>
9. China National Tourism Administration. (2013). Year book of China Tourism Statistics. Beijing:
10. National Tourism Administration of the People's Republic of China